

ECONOMIC IMPACTS

of the Finnish *Salmonella* Control Programme for Broilers

Economic evaluation team

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DESCRIPTION

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Abstract

The Finnish *Salmonella* Control Programme (FSCP) sets stricter demands on *Salmonella* control in the broiler production chain than does Council Directive 92/117/EEC, the so-called zoonosis directive, for EU member states. Surpassing the minimum demands creates extra costs for the Finnish broiler production chain. In addition to the FSCP in primary and secondary production, voluntary sampling for *Salmonella* is performed at all production levels, which further reduces the prevalence of *Salmonella* in foodstuffs. The goal of the FSCP is to prevent human *Salmonella* cases, thus minimizing health care costs to society. This project estimated the annual costs invested in the FSCP and compared this with the benefits it offers.

Costs of *Salmonella* control in the broiler production chain and human sickness due to *Salmonella* were calculated based on data for the year 2000. The current situation was then compared with an alternative scenario where broilers were tested only according to Council Directive 92/117/EC. The costs of the FSCP (including sampling according to the zoonosis directive) in 2000 were 991 870 d (5 897 393 FIM, median). Sampling based on the zoonosis directive alone would have resulted in costs of 84 196 d (500 607 FIM, median). FSCP costs in 2000 were 0.017 d/kg (0.10 FIM/kg) of broiler meat produced.

With the current prevalence of *Salmonella*, the approximate proportion of costs of the FSCP allocated to primary production is 38%, to secondary production 60% and to society 2%. Costs incurred by secondary production consist mainly of the stocking and heat-treating of *Salmonella*-positive flocks. Costs of voluntary samples in primary and secondary production were about 8% of total costs and 26% of sampling costs of the FSCP.

The cost-benefit ratio of the FSCP compared with *Salmonella* control according to Directive 92/117/EEC was found to be dependent mostly on the number of product withdrawals from the market and deaths. With the current prevalence of *Salmonella* in animals, even one prevented death was estimated to justify the FSCP.

The cost-benefit ratio of the FSCP versus compulsory control according to the zoonosis directive alone was calculated to be 0.59 when product withdrawal

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from the market and deaths were excluded and 4.40 (median) with their inclusion. This means that one invested Euro produces a 4.40 Euro profit. The win-lose ratio of the FSCP was calculated to be 39.155:1. When product withdrawal from the market and deaths were excluded, the win-lose ratio was 0.854:1. Win-lose figures of less than one represent loss per invested capital and figures greater than one represent profit. The distance from one describes the magnitude of the profit or loss.

The broiler production chain benefits from the FSCP by an improved product image. Deaths of broiler meat origin and product withdrawals from market likely have a strong impact on consumer choices.

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